

Future changes in multi-week heat extremes over the Waikato region: a preliminary assessment

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Key points:

Hamilton experienced an unusually persistent 15-day period of anomalously high temperatures in early February 2025. Anthropogenic climate change has made this heatwave both more likely and more intense, primarily due to the accumulation of past carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in the atmosphere. This also means that similarly unusual events will become increasingly common as annual greenhouse gas emissions remain high and global temperatures continue to rise. In fact, by 2070 (under a middle-of-the-road "SSP2-4.5" scenario of future emissions), three out of four summers in Hamilton will include a 15-day hot spell (that is, daily maximum temperatures averaged over 15 days) more intense than events which happened only once a decade in the recent climate (1984-2015). Once-a-decade 15-day hot spells in the second half of the century are also projected to be approximately 2°C hotter than equivalent events today. For every one degree increase in annual-mean temperatures around the wider New Zealand region, we expect a corresponding +1.4°C increase in the intensity of the hottest 15-day spell for an average summer over the Hamilton area.

Even as early as the 2050s, we could experience significant and oppressive multi-week heatwaves, including temperatures which could persist at or above 30°C for several weeks in a row (alongside similarly anomalous temperatures for many other parts of the country). After factoring in coincident low winds and the relatively high humidity which accompanied past events over the Waikato region, these scenarios present health risks for vulnerable members of the community if no adaptation plans are implemented.

Finally, it is also worth noting that we can't rule out the possibility of a record-shattering event affecting the North Island even in today's climate. We found an example of a five-day heatwave that could conceivably occur and would be several degrees hotter than anything seen in available observational records over large parts of the North Island. While primarily driven by internal climate variability, these record-shattering events are also much more likely to occur when the *rate* of global warming is exceptionally high ([Fischer et al. 2021](#)), as is the case right now ([Copernicus 2025](#)).

Heat extremes are going to become more intense in the future, so the introduction of adaptation plans will be needed to avoid worsening heat-related health impacts. The question of how much worse things get depends on how rapidly the global economy can be decarbonised.

1. Context

Between January 31 and February 14, 2025, high temperatures were recorded at Hamilton for an unusually persistent fifteen consecutive days. When comparing the hottest 15-day periods (based on 15-day mean daily maximum temperatures, hereafter termed Tx15d) for each year with hourly data available at Hamilton Airport (since 1993), the 2025 event was ranked second, behind January 26 - February 09, 1998, and marginally ahead of a 2019 event.

2. Data and methods

To understand how similarly hot events will change in both frequency and intensity in the future, we make use of [recently released climate projections](#) from the Ministry for the Environment. Specifically, we analyse six different global climate models which were dynamically downscaled to 12km resolution over New Zealand using the CCAM atmosphere-only regional climate model. Further, we use a bias-corrected version of this data set, which has daily maximum temperature data available at a 5km x 5km horizontal resolution, and focus on the area immediately around Hamilton, New Zealand.

Further details about the modelling framework can be found [here](#). Further details of the peer-reviewed model evaluation process, demonstrating the suitability of CCAM for the assessment of heat extremes over New Zealand, can be found [here](#). Further explanation of the bias correction methodology used can be found [here](#).

3. Event definition

For each model, we choose our event threshold to be the *third-ranked* Tx15d event recorded over the 1985-2014 "Historical" period. This is broadly consistent with a 1-in-10 year event: this choice reflects the approximate rarity of the 2025 observed event in today's climate but also recognises the sample size constraints of the available model projections. It is worth noting that if a more extreme event threshold was instead selected, past research points to predictable behaviour in the frequency of similar events increasing even more rapidly, alongside negligible differences in the intensification of equally-rare events – see [Fischer & Knutti \(2015\)](#) or [Harrington & Otto \(2018\)](#) for further details.

4. Results

Figure 1a presents time-series of Tx15d for each model, both for the Historical model experiment spanning 1985-2014, as well as a middle-of-the-road emissions scenario (SSP2-4.5), which covers the period 2015-2099. Note that all annual maxima have been calculated using a New Zealand hydrological year (so a Tx15d value for the year 2014 denotes the hottest 15-day spell between 01 July 2014 and 30 June 2015). Annual Tx15d data for each model are presented as an anomaly relative to each model's own event threshold: this was the third-ranked value recorded in the thirty-year historical period, with most models recording a value of between 27 and 28°C (see specific numbers listed next to each model name). Figure 1b presents a running tally of the fraction of years within a rolling 21-year window for which Tx15d exceeds the selected event threshold, starting at the beginning of the SSP2-4.5 experiment (i.e. the first 21-year window is centred on 2025 and spans 2015-2035). We (arbitrarily) choose to highlight when in the future more than 75% of years exceed this historical 1-in-10 year event over any 21-year window: this is analogous to when the protracted hot spell of 2025 becomes effectively a cool summer in the future. We find most models experience such changes by 2075 (see vertical lines in Fig 1b), with emergence occurring as early as 2045 (ACCESS-CM2) or as late as 2085 (EC-Earth).

Figure 2 presents the exact same information as Figure 1a but in a slightly different way. Specifically, if the Tx15d recorded for each model year was less than the historical event threshold, we colour the box grey; otherwise, the margin by which the event threshold was exceeded that year is presented. Most models regularly have 15-day hot spells in the second half of the 21st century which exceed the historical 1-in-10-year event by more than +2°C.

As demonstrated in Figure 3, it is important to emphasise that model spread in the speed with which twenty-first century changes in Tx15d occur over Hamilton can be largely explained by model differences in average warming rates over the wider New Zealand region. While faster warming models like ACCESS-CM2 show seemingly quite different projections to slower warming models like NorESM2-MM, these can be largely reconciled once regional

warming rates are considered. Taking all models together, we estimate that every one degree of additional (annual-mean) temperature rise over the New Zealand region (which is related to but not the same as global-mean warming) will correspond to the hottest 15-day spell in an average summer over the Waikato region intensifying by approximately +1.4°C.

4.1. Selected hot years

To illustrate the potential for noteworthy multi-week heatwaves to occur even earlier in the twenty-first century, Figures 4 to 6 present nationwide maps of absolute Tx15d temperatures (left-hand panels) and anomalies with respect to a January-February historical climatology (middle panels) for a sequence of selected events from selected models. Specifically, the top row of figure 4 shows the 15 days spanning Jan 28 to Feb 11, 2051, as simulated by the EC-Earth model; the middle row shows the 15 days spanning Jan 18 to Feb 01, 2038, as simulated by the GFDL-ESM4 model; while the bottom row shows the 15 days spanning Jan 24 to Feb 07, 2076, as simulated by the AWI-CM-1-1-MR. We note that these three case studies were selected to highlight events from average models and with consistently high temperatures over the entire 15 days (akin to the 2025 event) rather than a particularly extreme shorter-duration event which occurred within the 15-day window (examples of which are shown in the supplementary information). When looking at the time-series data on the right-hand panels, we find all three events record temperatures between 30 and 32°C almost consistently over a two-week period.

As exemplified by some of the more extreme events highlighted in the supplementary information (particularly Figs S1-S2), extreme heat over the Waikato region also rarely occurs in isolation, with many events co-occurring with extreme temperature anomalies over many other regions around the country, including the Bay of Plenty, Hawke's Bay, Wairarapa and Marlborough districts. While beyond the scope of this short analysis, future research will assess the regional co-occurrence of extreme temperatures across New Zealand in further detail.

4.2. The non-zero risks of a record-shattering North Island heat event

Finally, we highlight the potential for a record-shattering heat event, akin to the 1973 Canterbury heatwave or equally-unprecedented events seen elsewhere around the world in recent years ([Bartusek et al. 2022](#); [Ciavarella et al. 2021](#); [Fischer et al. 2023](#); [Cattiaux et al. 2024](#)), to occur over the North Island even in today's climate.

Specifically, we highlight a very extreme five-day heatwave simulated by the CNRM-CM6-1 model in January 2010 of the "Historical" experiment – that is, when background greenhouse gas concentrations and other boundary conditions were consistent with recent observations. As shown in Figure 6, this event produced temperature anomalies in exceedance of +10°C for five consecutive days over large swathes of the North Island, including Hamilton.

Such an event, while extremely unlikely to occur in any individual year, should equally not be ruled out as inconceivable. Rather, such events are physically plausible and consistent with our understanding of the full spectrum of internal climate variability which can produce unprecedented weather events in the presence of an underlying warming trend ([Gessner et al. 2021](#); [Fischer et al. 2021](#); [Lüthi et al. 2024](#)), particularly once our relatively short observational records for daily maximum temperature over New Zealand are taken into account ([Zeder et al. 2023](#); [Zeder & Fischer 2024](#)).

5. Summary

Heat extremes over land are becoming both more frequent and more intense due to anthropogenic climate change ([Seneviratne et al. 2021](#)). Here, we demonstrate that such events are also worsening in New Zealand, using a recent hot spell in the Waikato region to contextualise future changes in multi-week hot spells under a middle-of-the-road emissions scenario.

Figure 1: Panel (a) shows Tx15d for all years between 1993 and 2025, for which hourly data was available from the MetService weather station at Hamilton Airport (AWS-93173). Note that, to allow a like-for-like comparison between years, daily maximum temperatures were defined as the maximum of hourly instantaneous temperature measurements and hourly measurements were also first rounded to the nearest degree (all measurements before 2003 were only recorded after rounding to the nearest integer). The three coloured circles denote 1998, 2019 and 2025. Panel (b) shows the corresponding day-to-day evolution of daily maximum temperatures for each of these three selected years, including the 15-day time periods for which the Tx15d values were drawn.

Figure 2: Panel (a) shows the temporal evolution of annual Tx15d anomalies for each model for the “Historical” experiment (1984-2015) and SSP2-4.5 emissions scenario (2015-2099). Anomalies are presented with relative to each model’s specific event threshold (black dashed line), which is the third-ranked event recorded for each model over the Historical experiment, broadly consistent with a 1-in-10-year event (the corresponding magnitude of this event threshold is listed next to each model). Panel (b) considers the percentage of years which exceed this chosen event threshold for rolling 21-year windows across the SSP2-4.5 future scenario. The horizontal dashed line denotes when four out of five years (80%) record a Tx15d exceeding the event threshold; the coloured vertical lines denotes the central year of the first 21-year window where each model experiences emergence into this new climate (wherein the historical 1-in-10-year Tx15d event could thereafter be considered a cool summer).

Warming of the Hottest 15 Day Stretch of Each Summer

Figure 3: Time-series of future exceedances of each model's specific 1-in-10-year event threshold. Grey cells denote summers with a Tx15d which was cooler than the event threshold; all other colours show the margin by which the Tx15d recorded that year exceeded the event threshold.

Figure 4: Scatterplot comparing changes in annual-mean temperatures across the wider New Zealand region (34-47°S, 166.4-178.5°E) with corresponding changes in Tx15d over Hamilton. Annual anomalies were calculated with respect to a 1984-2015 reference period before 21-year running average values were calculated. Each circle presents the 21-year window centred on each decade of the SSP2-4.5 future projections, starting in 2030 (i.e. 2030, 2040, 2050 ... 2090). The 21-year windows centred on 2050 and 2090 are highlighted in the figure for each model.

Figure 5: Maps showing selected Tx15d events from individual model years in the future. For each row, the left-hand column presents 15-day mean daily maximum temperatures for the event of interest, the middle column shows the corresponding daily maximum temperature anomalies relative to a January-February climatology, and the right-hand column shows a time-series of daily maximum temperatures over the location of interest (Hamilton, see circle in each map), along with vertical dashed lines denoting the

15-day event of interest. Top row shows a Tx15d event from EC-Earth occurring in 2051; the middle row shows an event from GFDL-ESM4 occurring in 2038; and the bottom row shows an event from AWI-CM-1-1-MR occurring in 2076.

Figure 6: Same as Figure 5, but this time showing a shorter-duration five-day event which was simulated by CNRM-CM6-1 on Jan 24-28 2010. This event was selected for its prolonged and extreme intensity over many regions of the North Island, including the Waikato region (see right-hand panel).

Supplementary Information

Figure S1: Same as Figure 5 of the main manuscript but showing selected future events from the other three models: top row shows a 2065 event from CNRM-CM-6-1; the middle row shows a 2059 event from ACCESS-CM2; the bottom row shows a 2061 event from NorESM2.

Figure S2: Comparison of different methods to define Tx15d for the 2025 event at Hamilton airport. The dashed line with filled circles shows the true daily maximum temperatures recorded by the Hamilton Aero MetService station: these temperatures could occur at any time of the afternoon, not necessarily at the top of the hour, and would be what is shown in the 'Past Weather' section of the MetService website. The solid line time-series with no circles show daily maximum temperatures when defined based on 24 *instantaneous* observations at the top of each hour of the day (where those temperatures are recorded to one decimal place). Finally, the solid line with filled circles shows daily maximum temperatures based again only on these instantaneous hourly observations but after first rounding each hourly observation to the nearest degree (integer value). This latter option was chosen to be presented in Figure 1 of the main manuscript: this was because only hourly instantaneous observations already rounded to the nearest degree were available from the MetService automatic weather station at Hamilton Airport (AWS-93173) prior to 2003.